

Spikelet fertility percentage in indica varieties grown under different weather conditions. Hangzhou, China, 1989.

Variety	SFP at given heading date					Degree of reduction ^a (%)	Group ^b
	Normal weather	Wet weather					
	26 Jun	30 Jun	4 Jul	8 Jul	Mean		
88-7212	83.0	66.4	45.0	33.0	48.1	42.0	Susceptible
89-9382	64.9	38.5	45.7	29.7	38.0	41.5	Susceptible
89-9383	81.7	61.5	41.6	58.9	54.0	33.9	Susceptible
Cong-xie 39	87.1	74.1	54.8	50.4	59.8	31.3	Susceptible
Er-jiu-feng	87.4	66.8	65.5	56.4	62.9	28.0	Middle
HG8547	81.7	60.8	57.0	63.5	60.4	26.0	Middle
Zhen-yu 29	74.0	61.3	59.1	46.3	55.6	24.9	Middle
Ai-gan-shan-li-qi	79.2	55.2	57.2	71.2	61.2	22.7	Middle
Zhe-fu 802	85.8	75.6	55.3	70.1	67.0	21.9	Middle
Fu-lian-ai	83.6	65.3	69.2	66.6	67.0	19.8	Tolerant
6713	88.2	80.6	67.3	64.9	70.9	19.6	Tolerant
Guang-lu-ai 4	78.2	64.2	74.6	66.0	68.2	12.8	Tolerant
Mean	81.2 a	64.2 b	57.7 bc	56.4 c	59.4 bc	27.0	

^aDegree of reduction (%) = $\frac{\text{Maximum value} - \text{minimum value}}{\text{Maximum value}} \times 100$.

^bSFP degree of reduction for tolerant, intermediate, and susceptible varieties was <20, 20-30, and >30, respectively. ^cMeans followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Among varieties, SFP differed during normal weather and wet weather (see table). The varieties could be divided into three groups according to response to wet

weather. Guang-lu-ai 4, 6713, and Fulian-ai had higher SFP in wet weather than 88-7212 and 89-9382. ■

from 5 DAI to when a lesion stopped sporulating), and difference in infectivity (DIE, percent infected plants 7 DAI) were measured. Plants were observed every 2 h beginning 70 h after inoculation. One leaf lesion on each of 10 seedlings per variety was selected and its area measured. The leaf with lesion was placed in a glass tube containing 1 ml distilled water mixed with mercury bichloride, and left for 15 h.

Conidia samples were taken at 0800 h each day. Each glass tube was shaken vigorously to dislodge conidia and taken to the laboratory for counting. Conidia per lesion and per cm lesion area were calculated. Tubes with fresh solution were installed on the same lesions by 1700 h daily until sporulation ceased.

The partially resistant cultivars had slightly longer IP than susceptible check Yuan-Feng-Zao (see table). RIE on Xiang-Zhou No. 5, Zhe-Fu 802, and Er-Jiu-Feng were significantly less than on the susceptible check. With isolate ZC15, RIE of all test varieties was lower, indicating it is a less aggressive isolate. LS was significantly smaller on all partially resistant cultivars than on the susceptible check.

SC on all test varieties was lower than that from the susceptible check. SC on Zhu-Ke No. 2 was the lowest for both isolates.

DIE of Xiang-Zhou No. 5, Er-Jiu-Feng, and Zhu-Fu 802 were significantly lower than that of Zhu-Ke No. 2 and the susceptible check, and were much lower with isolate ZC15 (no infection on Xiang-Zhou No. 5). This indicates that isolate ZC15

Pest resistance—diseases

Some components of partial resistance to blast (BI) in indica rices

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Indica rice varieties Xiang-Zhou No. 5, Er-Jiu-Feng, Zhu-Ke No. 2, and Zhe-Fu 802 have shown relatively long-lasting resistance to BI (*Pyricularia oryzae*) in farmers' fields. In 1989, we evaluated some components of partial resistance, with Yuan-Feng-Zao as the susceptible check.

Seedlings selected for uniform growth were spray-inoculated with two pathogen isolates (10⁵ conidia/ml at 20 d after sowing). The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications of 20 seedlings each.

Incubation period (IP, time from inoculation to first appearance of lesions),

relative infection efficiency (RE, no. of lesions/plant 7 d after inoculation [DAI]), lesion size (LS, length and width of 20 randomly selected lesions from each replication, estimated in mm² [lesion length × width × 0.5]), sporulation capacity (SC, total no. of conidia produced

The components of partial resistance of 5 rice varieties inoculated with isolates of *P. oryzae*.^a Hangzhou, China, 1989.

Variety	RIE (lesions/plant)	LS ^b (mm ²)	SC ^c		IF (h)	DIE (%)
			Per lesion	Per cm ² lesion		
<i>Race ZBIS (0262)</i>						
Xiang-Zhou No. 5	1.53 c	1.13 c	2,983 b	99,667 bc	79.2 a	46.9 b
Er-Jiu-Feng	2.36 bc	1.80 c	2,850 b	124,000 bc	73.2 c	47.1 b
Zhu-Ke No. 2	3.78 ab	2.08 b	2,038 b	70,667 c	75.9 b	81.4 a
Zhe-Fu 802	2.32 c	1.84 b	4,133 a	155,500 ab	73.0 c	51.1 b
Yuan-Feng-Zao	4.20 a	3.34 a	4,160 a	192,200 a	71.0 d	95.1 a
<i>Race ZC15 (84-76)</i>						
Xiang-Zhou No. 5	0.00	---	---	---	---	---
Er-Jiu-Feng	1.71 ab	1.54 b	5,267 a	123,000 bc	74.0 bc	26.5 c
Zhu-Ke No. 2	1.94 ab	1.49 b	2,850 b	65,667 c	83.3 a	45.1 b
Zhe-Fu 802	1.44 b	0.71 b	3,000 b	146,167 ab	77.5 b	16.9 c
Yuan-Feng-Zao	2.21 a	4.12 a	5,830 a	217,800 a	71.6 c	84.8 a

^aIn each column, variety means followed by a common later are not significantly different by DMRT at P = 0.05. ^bData from 7 DAI. ^cMean number of conidia from samples taken 5, 7, 10, and 12 DAI.

was less aggressive, and that Xiang-Zhou No. 5 may have specific resistance genes effective against ZC15.

The cultivars that have shown durable resistance in the field have partial resistance to the races tested in this study. ■

Analysis of rice blast (BI) pathogen virulence in Egypt

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We evaluated the virulence of *Pyricularia oryzae* in B1-affected areas of the Nile Delta (governorates of Beheira, Dakhalia, Damietta, Gharbia, and Kafr el Sheikh) 1988-89 summer seasons.

Rice leaves and panicles with typical B1 lesions were collected from farmers' fields. Single lesions were placed in petri dishes with wet filter paper and incubated at 25°C until sporulation.

A group of conidia was aseptically transferred with a pointed capillary tube to rice leaf agar. For the purpose of this study, mass cultures from single lesions were considered equivalent to single conidial isolates. (Previous studies under the same test conditions had indicated that single conidial cultures derived from single lesions are of one race.)

In 1988, 10 commercial cultivars and 8 international differentials were tested against 35 isolates. In 1989, 8 commercial cultivars and international differentials were tested against 52 isolates.

Test plants grown in 40- × 20- × 10-cm plastic boxes in 10-cm rows, 5 cm apart were inoculated with aqueous spore

P. oryzae isolates virulent to commercial rice cultivars in Egypt 1988 and 1989.

Cultivar	Virulence ^a (%)	
	1988 (n=35)	1989 (n=52)
Giza 159	100	100
Giza 171	100	100
Giza 172	100	100
Reiho	100	100
Giza 175	3 ^b	2 ^a
Giza 181	0	0
GZ1368-5-4	0	nt
GZ2175-5-6	20	53
IR28	0	0
IR50	0	nt

^a (n) = number isolates tested. nt = not tested. ^b Intermediate reaction.

suspension (about 50,000/ml). Inoculated plants were left in a moist chamber for 48 h, then transferred to the greenhouse. Disease was scored 10-15 d later.

B1 virulence on local cultivars Giza 159, Giza 171, Giza 172, and Reiho was 100% both years (see table). Virulence was zero on indica cultivars IR28, IR50, and Giza 181, and rare on Giza 175. Currently popular breeding line GZ2175-5-6 was affected by 20% of the isolates in 1988 and 53% in 1989 (see table).

This increase in virulence on GZ2175-5-6 is associated with an increase in area sown to this line, from 1,000 ha in 1988 to 10,000 ha in 1989. ■

Resistance to blast (BI) in Egyptian rice varieties

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B1 is a major production constraint in Egypt. Resistance in a series of japonica varieties released in 1954-84 was short. A few indica breeding lines (IR28, IR1626-203 [Giza 181]) released in recent years retain resistance, but they have limited commercial acceptability and narrow genetic bases.

We evaluated 500 improved cultivars, breeding lines, and germplasm of diverse origin against the prevailing B1 pathogen races ID13 and IG1 in the Nile Delta.

Entries grown in the greenhouse were inoculated with two representative isolates of *Pyricularia oryzae* 15 d after sowing (DAS). Temperature was maintained at 21-32°C and relative humidity at >90% for 9-11 h. Cultivars found to be resistant 45 DAS are listed in Table 1.

Fifteen varieties were evaluated against three representative virulent isolates from the rice-growing delta. Entries planted in single rows in nursery boxes were inoculated at 15 DAS with virulent isolates originating from Dakhalia, Kafr el Sheikh, and Gharbia governorates. After 48 h in the humid chamber, they were transferred to glass-house benches. Disease was recorded 15 d later.

All tested IRRI varieties were resistant to the local B1 pathogen races (Table 2). Some of the varieties (IR50, Ratna,

Table 1. Reaction of selected rice genotypes to 2 representative *Pyricularia oryzae* isolates of Egypt.

Cultivar	Reaction to <i>P. oryzae</i> isolates	
	ID13 ^a	IG1 ^b
IRRI		
IR20	1	1
IR22	1	1
IR24	1	2
IR28	1	1
IR36	1	1
IR50	1	1
IR52	1	1
IR60	1	1
IR62	1	1
IR64	1	1
IR66	1	1
IR2003-P18-16	1	1
IR2153-338-3	1	1
IR19743-46-1	1	1
IR25571-31-1	1	1
Thailand		
RD7	1	1
RD9	1	1
RD10	1	1
RD21	1	1
RD25	1	1
S. Korea		
Iri 370	1	1
Milyang 23	2	1
Milyang24	2	1
Milyang 80	2	1
Milyang 85	2	1
Suweon 346	1	1
Japan		
BL 1	1	1
Kanto 1	1	2
Tsuyuuake	1	3
Toride 1	1	1
India		
Bala	1	1
Basmati 370	1	1
Cauvery	1	1
CO 43	1	1
Padma	2	4
Ratna	1	1
Rasi	1	1
Tella hamsa	1	1
USA		
Mars	1	1
Lemont	1	1
Mercury	1	1
Noritai	1	1
Egypt		
Agami	3	4
Giza 175	2	1
Giza 181	1	1
Giza2175-5-6	8	2
Yabani 15 (susceptible)	7	8
Giza 159 (susceptible)	8	8
Giza 172 (susceptible)	8	8
Reiho (susceptible)	8	8

^a Isolate from Sidisalem, on Giza on 2175-5-6. ^b Isolate from RRTC research farm Sakha, on Giza 172.

Cauvery) have a history of susceptibility in the tropics. IR36, Rasi, and a few